

THE CONCEPT, ESSENCE, AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE REGION'S EXPORT POTENTIAL.

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Annotation: This paper explores the concept, essence, and classification of regional export potential, highlighting its role in ensuring sustainable economic growth and competitiveness in international markets.

Key words: export potential, region, concept

The concept of 'region' is a relatively new term and is associated with a new branch of economics – 'Regional Economics.' The Russian scholar N.N. Nekrasov was the first to define it in 1975 as follows: 'A region is understood as a large territory of a country characterized by the development of production capacities, based on the combination of more or less uniform natural conditions, as well as the available material and technical base, production, and social infrastructure in accordance with natural resources [1].

Most economists have proposed dividing the territory of Uzbekistan into six economic regions. In recent years, however, some economists have suggested reducing the number of economic regions to four. In general, the majority of economists have divided the republic into the following six economic regions:

1. Tashkent (Tashkent city and Tashkent region);
2. Fergana (Fergana, Andijan, and Namangan regions);
3. Zarafshan (Bukhara, Navoi, and Samarkand regions);
4. Mirzachul (Syrdarya and Jizzakh regions);
5. Southern (Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions);
6. Lower Amudarya (Aral Sea area, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and Khorezm region) [2].

Based on the study of approaches in economic literature, we divided them into the following general groups:

The first group of scholars take the socio-geographical characteristics of territorial units as the main criterion;

The second group emphasize the integrity of social reproduction within regions;

The third group classify according to national, state, and administrative-territorial boundaries;

The fourth group differentiate based on the territorial distribution of productive forces, as well as the forms of agro-industrial and free economic zones.

Foreign trade activity is an entrepreneurial activity in the field of international trade in goods, works (services). Foreign trade activity is carried out through the export and import of goods, works (services). The removal of goods from the customs territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan without the obligation to bring them back, unless otherwise stipulated by legislation, is considered export. One of the terms that is widely used in today's scientific field is 'export potential.' Due to the fact that it introduces a number of new conceptual aspects for our national economy, it encourages a deeper study of this phenomenon. The concept of 'potential' refers to the aggregation and consolidation of resources within a certain space and time [3]. The concept of

‘economic potential,’ in turn, expresses the level of provision of society with material and human resources, the extent of opportunities for their utilization, and is evaluated according to the scale of these opportunities. The assessment of economic potential should begin with the evaluation of natural and human resources, since the essence of the economy lies in optimally satisfying the unlimited needs of humanity through limited resources. The foundation of production, in this context, is formed by raw material resources and human labor.

Considering export potential merely as a development opportunity represents a narrow and one-sided approach, as it disregards its actual (real) form. At the same time, the etymology of the term ‘potential’ (from the English word potential – opportunity, capacity, power) also implies its use in evaluating the capabilities of a particular system. The term ‘potential’ carries a broader meaning than ‘opportunity.’ The latter may be understood as a component of the process of movement and development, or even as the functional ‘potential’ of that process. In particular, during the study of the concept of ‘export potential,’ the definitions and perspectives provided by several foreign and domestic scholars were examined. As a result, the following ten definitions were summarized according to a number of indicators [4].

In this research, an attempt has been made to provide a more advanced definition of this concept, and the author proposes the following definition of export potential: Export potential is the ability of the national economy, regions, individual sectors, or enterprises to produce and supply, in sufficient quantities, competitive goods and services for export.

Table 1.

Definitions of the Concept of “Export Potential” in Encyclopedic Dictionaries

Name of Encyclopedic Dictionary	Definition of the Concept
“Encyclopedic Dictionary of Economics and Law”	Export potential is the ability of a state to export existing resources or products manufactured domestically.
“Economic Dictionary”	Export potential is the possibility and potential capacity of a country to export existing or domestically produced resources and products.
“Dictionary of Business Terms”	Export potential is the ability to produce, in the required quantities, goods that meet global market standards in terms of quality and competitiveness, with the purpose of exporting them.
“New Economic Dictionary”	Export potential is the ability of a country’s industry and overall social production to manufacture competitive products in the required volume and supply them to the foreign market.

In our opinion, depending on the level of utilization, export potential can be divided into two parts: active and passive export potential. Active export potential refers to the part of the total export potential that is actually utilized. In other words, it is the sum of opportunities for producing competitive goods and services that are exported to world markets or foreign countries.

Figure 1. The Level of Utilization of Export Potential

Passive export potential, on the other hand, refers to the ability to produce competitive goods and services that meet certain international standards, but which cannot be utilized for various reasons. For example, although goods and services can be produced, they may not be exported due to the absence of a convenient and affordable transport system for delivery to world markets, or because they do not meet foreign technical requirements, among other factors. In our view, improving the rational use of a region’s export potential should be understood as the activation of its passive export potential.

The circle in the figure conditionally represents the total export potential of a country or region. The distinctiveness of the definition of ‘export potential’ proposed by us, compared to the approaches of other scholars who have studied this concept, lies in the fact that it encompasses both the common and differentiating aspects of each approach. In particular, export potential exists not only at the macro level, but also at the levels of regions, individual sectors, and enterprises. Moreover, it is assessed not only through the production of competitive tangible goods for the world market, but also through the provision of services [5]. In addition, within this dissertation, a classification of the factors shaping regional export potential has been developed.

It should be noted that most of the definitions and approaches to the concept of export potential are of purely theoretical significance and do not reveal the methods or mathematical formulas by which it can be calculated and evaluated. In this research, we not only approached the concept of export potential from a theoretical-analytical perspective, but also focused on the methodology of its calculation and assessment. As a result of the conducted studies, we developed a rating-based method for evaluating export potential.

Table 2.

Factors Influencing Regional Export Potential

I. Indirect influencing factors	II. Direct influencing factors
1. Natural and geographical environment	1. GDP
2. State policy	2. Regional foreign trade turnover
3. Economic environment	3. Regional retail trade turnover
4. International environment	4. Investment in fixed capital, including foreign investments
5. Socio-demographic environment	5. Volume of industrial products
	6. Cash income of the population

The purpose of the regional export potential ranking is to provide a quantitative assessment of the export potential and determine its position among other regions. The indicators were brought into a single, systematic, comparable form using the formulas below. They are; per capita regional foreign trade turnover, investments, industrial output, agricultural output, services, foreign trade turnover of joint ventures;

- number of individual entrepreneurs;
- number of established enterprises (in% compared to the beginning of the year);
- employment rate in joint ventures;
- output of small business enterprises per small business enterprise;
- share of enterprises and population in total investments;
- number of jobs in small businesses;
- level of openness of the regional economy;
- share of foreign investment in total investments;
- capital import coefficient (foreign investment) [6].

The assessment represents a ranking of regions based on their aggregated results in terms of indicators. The level of development of the country's economy and the volume of GDP largely depend on the country's export potential and how rationally it is used. World experience in the rational use of export potential shows that each country, depending on its economic conditions, stage of development, and the economic and political situation in the world, has used different methods of stimulating exports. Countries have encouraged their exporters, relying more on market mechanisms as a means of state intervention. Thus, stimulating exports through state intervention has yielded positive results, especially in the export of non-traditional exports or modern technically complex products that require significant investment in the organization of production and their introduction to the world market. In this situation, the state's financial support, its efforts to mobilize private investment, and the laying of infrastructure have become of great importance and have ensured the improvement of export structures in a relatively short period of time.

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